

4-Bromomethylcoumarins. Synthesis from Phenols and γ -Bromoacetoacetic Ester.

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It has been shown in an earlier investigation (Dey and Radhabai, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 635) that a mixture of coumarin-4-bromoacetic acid and 4-bromomethylcoumarins are produced when coumarin-4-acetic acids are brominated under certain definite conditions. The constitution assigned to these bromo derivatives was based on indirect though sufficiently clear evidence, but as the reactivity of the halogen in these compounds was very different from what might be expected of an alkyl bromide, it was considered expedient to obtain direct proofs, if possible, of the structure of these bromomethylcoumarins. It was believed that one of the best methods of settling the question would be to synthesise the same compounds from phenols and γ -bromoacetoacetic ester and our expectations in this direction have now been fully realised. The condensations of *m*-cresol and α -naphthol with γ -bromoacetoacetic ester have now been studied and the products shown to be identical with those prepared from 7-methylcoumarin-4-acetic acid and α -naphthopyrone-4-acetic acid respectively by bromination, thus setting at rest all doubts regarding the position of the bromine atom in these compounds. Moreover, the view that β -naphthopyrone-4 acetic acid proved to be an exception in furnishing not the expected β -naphthopyrone-4-bromoacetic acid but the 3-bromo- β -naphthopyrone-4-acetic acid instead, has now been fully confirmed by synthesising the unknown 4-bromomethyl- β -naphthopyrone. The latter (m. p. 197°) is found to be quite different from the product of bromination of β -naphthopyrone-4-acetic acid after decarboxylation (m. p. 146°), and it is further converted by hot alkalis into the expected dihydrofuranonylacetic acid (m. p. 174°) and not the β -naphthafurancarboxylic acid (m. p. 242°) obtained by Dey and Radhabai (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

γ -Bromoacetoacetic ester was prepared by a slight modification of the method described by Conrad and Schmidt (*Ber.*, 1896, 29, 1042).

From 13 g. of freshly distilled acetoacetic ester 11 g. of the pure γ -bromo derivative, b. p. $125^{\circ}/10$ mm. were obtained.

7-Methyl-4-bromomethylcoumarin.—A mixture of γ -bromoacetoacetic ester (6 g.) and *m*-cresol (3 g.) was slowly added to ice-cold sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) with vigorous shaking and after standing in the ice-chest overnight, the deep red liquid was poured in a thin stream into 150 c.c. of ice water. A fine yellowish precipitate came down slowly; it was collected, washed with water and then with alcohol and the insoluble residue crystallised from boiling acetic acid as colourless shining plates, m. p. 236° , not depressed by admixture with the specimen obtained from the direct bromination of 7-methylcoumarin-4-acetic acid.

6-Methylbenzodihydrofuranonyl-3-acetic acid was obtained by the action of alkali on the bromo derivative. It crystallised from boiling water in long colourless needles, m. p. 107° , and was identified with the product prepared similarly from 7-methylcoumarin-4-acetic acid by bromination and subsequent alkali treatment (Dey and Radhabhai, *loc. cit.*).

4-Bromomethyl- α -naphthapyrone.—The thick yellow oil which separated on pouring the sulphuric acid solution of α -naphthol (4 g.) and the γ -bromoacetoacetic ester (6 g.) into water was converted into a granular yellow solid after repeated washing with alcohol. Two crystallisations from hot acetic acid gave bright yellow plates, m. p. 192° , yield 1 g. It was identified with the product of bromination of α -naphthapyrone-4-acetic acid by a mixed m. p. determination. (Found: C, 58.1; H, 3.34; Br, 27.1. $C_{14}H_9O_2Br$ requires C, 58.1; H, 3.11; Br, 27.7 per cent).

α -Naphthodihydrofuranonyl-3-acetic acid was obtained from the above by boiling with 2N-KOH for 20 minutes. It crystallised from boiling water in colourless needles, m. p. 162° . (Found: C, 73.9; H, 4.69. $C_{14}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 74.3; H, 4.42 per cent).

4-Bromomethyl- β -naphthapyrone.— β -Naphthol (4 g.) and the bromoester (6 g.) were treated with sulphuric acid and the product worked up as before. It crystallised from acetic acid in golden yellow rectangular plates, m. p. 197° . (Found: C, 57.7; H, 3.39; Br, 27.1. $C_{14}H_9O_2Br$ requires C, 58.1; H, 3.11; Br, 27.7 per cent).

β-Naphthadihydrofuranonyl-3-acetic acid.

This was prepared by boiling the bromomethyl derivative with 2*N*-alkali for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The acid crystallised from hot water in pale yellow needles, m. p. 172°. It decolourises bromine water and permanganate immediately in the cold. (Found: C, 74.1 ; H, 4.62. $\text{C}_{14} \text{H}_{10} \text{O}_3$ requires C, 74.3; H, 4.42 per cent).

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